

Synthesis and spectral properties of palladium(II) complexes derived from 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole thiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbazates

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Abstract : Some new palladium(II) complexes of S-methyl-, S-benzyl- β -N-(5-methylpyrazole-3-yl)methylenedithiocarbamate and 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole 3-pyrrolidinyl-, 4 N-benzylthiosemicarbazone have been synthesized and characterized by spectroscopic methods. The spectral studies reveal the square planar geometry of the palladium(II) complexes where the ligand molecule acts as uninegative tridentate with NNS donor sites.

Keywords : Palladium(II), dithiocarbazates, tridentate ligands, pyrazolylthiosemicarbazones.

Heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and the related ligands and also their complexes have attracted much attention both in chemistry and biology due to their biological potentiality¹. It is likely that the biological activity is due to ability to form tridentate chelates with essential heavy metal ion bonding through NNS donor sites. Though the mechanism of biological activities not yet been established², however, the reasons may be included; (1) replacement of the sulphur atom of the thiocarbonyl group by oxygen, selenium, an imine, an oxime etc., (2) modification of sulphur center by alkylation, (3) changing the thiosemicarbazone moiety's point of attachment on the heterocyclic ring, (4) substitution on the terminal 4 N position and (5) variation of the nature of aldehyde or ketone.

As a part of a comprehensive work³⁻⁶ on the complexes of pyrazolyl thiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbazates to correlate structural aspect with biological activity we report herein the synthesis of newly prepared palladium(II) complexes of S-methyl- β -N-(5-methylpyrazole-3-yl)methylenedithiocarbamate (HMPzSMe), S-benzyl- β -N-(5-methylpyrazole-3-yl)methylenedithiocarbamate (HMPzSB), 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole- 4 N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB) and 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-pyrrolidinylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzPyr) (Fig. 1). Synthesis and spectroscopic studies have been carried out in order to obtain information on structure-activity relationship for the system involving palladium(II) atom.

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

All the prepared complexes were sparingly soluble in methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, acetonitrile and go readily into solution in donor solvents like DMSO and DMF. The elemental analyses of the reported palladium complexes are given in Table 1. All are diamagnetic and non-electrolytes consistent with the coordination of the halo ligands.

Spectral studies :

The significant electronic absorption bands in the spectra of the complexes are presented in Table 2. The electronic spectra of the complexes are dominated by the intra ligand ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $n \rightarrow \pi^*$) and charge transfer transitions in the high energy regions. However, the spectra has one low intensity broad band in the region *ca.* 15000 cm^{-1} both in solid and solution spectra being recognized as the usual *d-d* band which are resemble to

Table 1. Colour and elemental analyses of the palladium(II) complexes

Comps.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Pd
[Pd(MPzSMe)Cl]	Light yellow	23.7 (23.6)	2.2 (2.50)	15.8 (15.7)	29.7 (29.9)
[Pd(MPzSMe)Br]	Light yellow	21.1 (21.0)	2.2 (2.2)	14.2 (14.0)	26.4 (26.6)
[Pd(MPzSB)Cl]	Yellow	36.3 (36.2)	2.9 (3.0)	13.1 (12.9)	24.5 (24.7)
[Pd(MPzSB)Br]	Light yellow	32.8 (32.8)	2.6 (2.7)	11.8 (11.7)	22.4 (22.3)
[Pd(MPzNB)Cl]	Yellow	38.0 (37.8)	3.2 (3.1)	17.1 (16.9)	25.7 (25.8)
[Pd(MPzNB)Br]	Light yellow	34.2 (34.1)	2.8 (2.8)	15.4 (15.3)	23.1 (23.3)
[Pd(MPzPyr)Cl]	Light yellow	31.9 (31.7)	3.6 (3.7)	18.6 (18.5)	28.0 (28.1)
[Pd(MPzPyr)Br]	Light yellow	28.6 (28.4)	3.2 (3.3)	16.7 (16.5)	25.0 (25.2)

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of the reported palladium(II) complexes

Complexes	State	Frequencies (log ϵ L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	
		Intra ligand and CT	<i>d</i> → <i>d</i>
Pd(MPzSMe)Cl	Solid	24850 (0.91)	15200 (0.83)
	solution	32250 (4.32)	16300 (2.21)
Pd(MPzSMe)Br	Solid	23880 (0.92)	14960 (0.82)
	solution	32200 (4.4)	16200 (2.30)
Pd(MPzSB)Cl	Solid	25200 (0.9)	15300 (0.78)
	solution	32300 (4.4)	15750 (2.3)
Pd(MPzSB)Br	Solid	23250 (0.9)	14910 (0.8)
	solution	30880 (4.2)	16450 (0.75)
Pd(MPzNB)Cl	Solid	24500 (0.8)	15550 (2.3)
	solution	32250 (3.8)	16100 (2.20)
Pd(MPzNB)Br	Solid	24350 (0.82)	14500 (2.20)
	solution	32700 (3.8)	16400 (2.16)
Pd(MPzPyr)Cl	Solid	25500 (1.0)	14300 (0.7), 14100 (0.7)
	solution	29250 (4.01)	15350 (2.11)
Pd(MPzPyr)Br	Solid	23875 (0.93)	14900 (0.8)
	solution	32200 (4.10)	16650 (2.20)

those shown by the other palladium(II) complexes of NNS ligand for which square planar structure have been proposed⁷.

Some characteristic spectral changes have been no-

ticed in the IR spectra of the palladium complexes when compared to that of the free ligand (Table 3); these are enumerated below : (i) The sharp band at *ca.* 1550 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand spectrum due to $\nu_{\text{CH=N}}$ (azom) has been found to shift to a lower frequency region by $\Delta\nu = 30\text{--}60$ cm⁻¹ indicating a coordination through nitrogen atom of the azomethine linkage. (ii) The free ligand band at *ca.* 1500 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (pyrazole) vibration has been shifted to higher wave length ($\Delta\nu = 60\text{--}80$ cm⁻¹) supporting the involvement of the tertiary (²N) ring nitrogen atom as a bonding site. (iii) A sharp band at *ca.* 1000 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ (pyrazole) vibration in the free ligand spectrum is also shifted to the higher wave numbers by *ca.* 40 cm⁻¹ on complexation with a metal ion an additional support to the participation of the pyrazolyl nitrogen (²N) in bonding. (iv) The downward shift of the $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ band (800 cm⁻¹) in the free ligand by *ca.* 70–80 cm⁻¹ indicates the strong coordination of the sulphur atom to the metal ions in complex formation. The above proposition regarding bonding sites of the ligand molecule in complex formation is further supported by the bands appearing in the range *ca.* 480 to 500 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{\text{Pd-N}}$ (azomethine), *ca.* 210 to 280 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{\text{Pd-N}}$ (pyrazole), *ca.* 310–370 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ and *ca.* 250–290 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{\text{Pd-X}}$ vibration (X = Cl, Br). It is quite reasonable to accept that the ligand molecules behave in general, as mono deprotonated NNS tridentate ligand when complexed with palladium(II).

The comparison of ¹H NMR spectra of the reported palladium(II) complexes (Table 4) with that of the free ligand spectrum points out the following : (i) slightly downfield ($\delta = 7.24\text{--}7.20$) shift in δ -values are shown by both the benzylic and benzene ring protons in the complexes of HMPzNB and also the slightly downfield ($\delta = 4.45\text{--}4.52$) shift of -SCH₂- protons in the complexes derived from HMPzSB, which are ascribed to coordination of the thiol sulphur to palladium(II), (ii) maximum downfield shift occurs with the methine proton appearing at *ca.* $\delta = 8.40$ in the complexes corresponding to *ca.* $\delta = 7.87$ in the respective free ligand(s) as expected due to coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to palladium(II) and (iii) the shifting of ⁴CH (pyrazole ring) from *ca.* $\delta = 6.31$ (free ligand) to *ca.* $\delta = 6.50$ in complexes is quite reasonable with the proposition that ²N (pyrazole) coordinates with palladium(II). ¹H NMR spectra thus provide support for the bonding characteristics of the ligand(s) in forming complexes with palladium(II) through pyrazolyl ring nitrogen (²N), azomethine nitrogen and the thiolato sulphur atom⁸.

Table 3. Some characteristic IR bands (in cm^{-1}) of the palladium(II) complexes

Compds.	$\nu_{\text{CH=N}}$ (azom)	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (pz)	$\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ (pz)	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (pz)	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (azom)	$\nu_{\text{M-S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-X}}$
HMPzSMe	1620	1410	1030	830	-	-	-	-
[Pd(MPzSMe)Cl]	1570	1420	1060	800	380	520	310	280
[Pd(MPzSMe)Br]	1550	1420	1040	800	370	520	310	280
HMPzSB	1618	1580	1015	845	-	-	-	-
[Pd(MPzSB)Cl]	1560	1490	1090	800	470	540	320	250
[Pd(MPzSB)Br]	1560	1470	1075	820	470	520	360	270
HMPzNB	1550	1505	1010	800	-	-	-	-
[Pd(MPzNB)Cl]	1480	1585	1040	700	280	510	330	268
[Pd(MPzNB)Br]	1480	1580	1050	700	280	470	340	268
HMPzPyr	1570	1440	1010	860	-	-	-	-
[Pd(MPzPyr)Cl]	1490	1380	1080	800	540	330	400	280
[Pd(MPzPyr)Br]	1450	1350	1050	815	470	290	380	290

Table 4. PMR assignments of the ligands and its palladium(II) complexes (in δ ppm) relative to TMS

Compds.	Imino proton	Position of protons (pyrazolyl ring)			Methine proton	Benzylic proton	Bz/Pyr ring protons
		1	4	5			
HMPzSMe	12.94 8.15	13.16	6.31	2.27	7.45		3.35 (SCH ₃)
[Pd(MPzSMe)Cl]	-	14.20	6.70	2.48	8.86		3.32 (SCH ₃)
[Pd(MPzSMe)Br]	-	14.23	6.74	2.46	8.85		3.33 (SCH ₃)
HMPzSB	12.93 8.81	13.20	6.31	2.21	7.41	4.45	
[Pd(MPzSB)Cl]	-	14.40	6.76	2.30	8.92	4.52	
HMPzNB	11.68 8.00	12.87	6.34	2.26	7.87	4.79	7.29
[Pd(MPzNB)Cl]	-	13.76	6.46	2.46	8.40	4.50	7.24
[Pd(MPzNB)Br]	-	13.76	6.48	2.44	8.40	4.50	7.24
HMPzPyr	12.65 8.02	13.36	6.31	2.26	7.30		1.18-1.31 2.17-2.24
[Pd(MPzPyr)Cl]	-	13.80	6.48	2.44	8.32		1.34-2.18
[Pd(MPzPyr)Br]	-	13.76	6.47	2.44	8.34		1.34-2.18

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

AnalaR grade reagents and freshly distilled methanol were used in syntheses. The ligands have been synthesized according to the literature procedure⁹. Spectrograde solvents were used for spectral and conductance measurements. Solvent DMSO-*d*₆ (Sigma) used for recording ¹H NMR data. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out at IACS, Kolkata with Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400. The palladium content of the complexes were determined gravimetrically as bisdimethylglyoximatopalladium(II). The electronic spectra of the com-

plexes in DMF solution (ca. 30 °C) were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer model 833 infrared spectrophotometer with KBr pellets and magnetic measurements were made in a PAR 155 sample vibrating magnetometer at IACS, Kolkata. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ with a Bruker AM3002 (300 MHz) super conducting FT NMR.

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes of palladium(II) were prepared by reacting Li₂[PdX₄] (X = Cl and Br) in methanolic or aqueous solution of the ligand. Attempts to isolate complexes having the stoichiometry [Pd(HL)₂X₂] (where HL repre-

sents the neutral ligand molecule) and single crystals of the prepared complexes still are unsuccessful.

Preparation of [Pd(MPzSMe)X] (X = Cl and Br) : To a boiling solution of HMPzSMe (0.21 g, 1.00 mmol) in dry methanol (20 ml) is added lithium tetrahalogenopalladate(II), Li_2PdX_4 which prepared *in situ* from PdCl_2 and LiX (PdCl_2 , 0.192 g, 1.08 mmol; LiCl, 0.173 g, 4.08 mmol or LiBr, 0.354 g, 4.08 mmol respectively) in methanol (30 ml). The reaction mixture is stirred for 24 h at room temperature and then kept for overnight. The compounds are filtered off, washed with cold methanol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel. Yields 80% for [Pd(MPzSMe)Cl] and 70% for [Pd(MPzSMe)Br].

Preparation of [Pd(MPzSB)X] (X = Cl and Br) : To a boiling solution of HMPzSB (0.290 g, 1.00 mmol) in dry methanol (10 ml) is added lithium tetrahalogenopalladate(II), Li_2PdX_4 which prepared *in situ* from PdCl_2 and LiX (PdCl_2 , 0.2 g, 1.13 mmol; LiCl, 2.40 g, 5.6 mmol or LiBr, 0.40 g, 4.5 mmol respectively) in methanol (20 ml) and the resulting brownish yellow solution is stirred for 30 min at around [Pd(MPzSMe)X] (X = Cl and Br) around 90 °C upon slow evaporation, solid powdered are obtained in each case. The compounds are filtered off, washed with cold methanol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel. Yields 75% for [Pd(MPzSB)Cl] and 70% for [Pd(MPzSB)Br].

Preparation of [Pd(MPzNB)X] (X = Cl and Br) : The ligand HMPzNB (0.68 g, 0.0025 mmol) is dissolved in dry methanol (50 ml) is mixed with lithium tetrahalogenopalladate(II), Li_2PX_4 which prepared *in situ* from PdCl_2 and LiX (X = Cl and Br) (1 : 4 molar ratio) in the same solvent (10 ml) at 90 °C with constant stirring furnished yellow color solution. The desired mono complexes are precipitated out on cooling to room temperature. The complexe in each case is collected by filtration, wash with aqueous ethanol and dried over silica gel. Yields 70% for [Pd(MPzSNB)Cl] and 65% for [Pd(MPzSNB)Br].

Preparation of [Pd(MPzPyr)X] (X = Cl and Br) : A solution of ligand HMPzPyr (2.37 g, 0.01 mmol) in dry methanol (40 ml) is mixed with lithium tetrahalogenopalladate(II), Li_2PdX_4 which prepared *in situ* from PdCl_2 and LiX (X = Cl and Br) (1 : 4 molar ratio) in the same solvent (10 ml), the resulting solution was refluxed for 1 h. Upon slow evaporation of the resulting solution

at room temperature light yellow solids gradually precipitated out in case; these were filtered off; washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in air. Yield *ca.* 70% in each case.

Conclusion :

The most plausible structure (Fig. 2), based on so far available spectroscopic results for Pd(L)X (where L represents mono deprotonated ligand molecule) is square planar where the ligand molecule acts as uninegative tridentate with NNS donor sites.

Fig. 2

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